

Predicting U.S. Stock Sectors Using AI-Driven News Sentiment Analysis

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Abstract

This paper explores the predictability of U.S stock sectors using an AI-driven sentiment analysis model. This is a logistic regression model that analyzes news headlines and predicts stock fluctuations. Using approximately 11,000 GDELT news headlines from 2017 to 2025, the model generates trading signals, which are then backtested by sector. The results of the model show the Sharpe ratios, a reliable measure of an investment's return relative to its risk, for each sector. The model has both an unbalanced and a balanced mode: the unbalanced mode predicts each sector based on its frequency in the news, whilst the balanced mode predicts each sector with an equal number of trades per sector. Our results show that the technology and financial sectors appear to be consistent and highly correlated (Sharpe ratios of 0.6 to 1.1) with news headlines. Conversely, the healthcare and real estate sectors have negative Sharpe ratios, indicating poor tradability based on news headlines. In summary, AI-driven news sentiment analysis may be dependent on sectors and their frequency in news headlines.

Keywords: Sentiment Analysis; Stock Prediction; Financial Sectors; Logistic Regression; News Analytics; Sharpe Ratio

1 Introduction

The stock market is dictated by public sentiment and the concept of buyers and sellers. The most influential source of information that influences public sentiment is the news. Sentiment often drives short-term stock market fluctuations and can be a great indicator of stock prices. Most studies focus on individual stocks or the overall market. On the contrary, in this paper, we discuss the implications of news headlines on specific sectors in the market. We test the following hypotheses:

- **H1:** News-headline sentiment can predict next-day stock returns.

- **H2:** News-driven tradability differs by sector, with some sectors expressing stronger risk-adjusted performance.

We used a logistic regression model to predict whether a stock will increase or decrease based on the news headlines. The model gathers news headlines, analyzes sentiment using VADER, fits the data to a logistic regression, and lastly outputs the probability that the stock will rise on the next day. A logistic regression was used for a clean and simple ranking of the probability that the stock will rise; more complex models will have a risk of overfitting. We can compute performance metrics for this partitioned by sector, and use this to authenticate our hypotheses. Using this pipeline, trading in the technology sector had the highest Sharpe ratio. Other sectors are weaker due to low news coverage and limited signals. In creating this model, we have made a reproducible pipeline that establishes a correlation between news headlines and company sectors. Sector analysis in the stock market is particularly useful because each industry responds differently to news and earnings cycles. A limitation of our model is that, after running a significance test, we found that most sectors had high p-values. However, this reflects limited statistical significance rather than an absence of a correlation. In this paper, we will be discussing data collection, methodology, results, limitations, and future work.

2 Related Works

Previous studies have shown that there is a link between financial news and stock prices. In a study conducted by Paul Tetlock, he found that the textual tone in the media directly relates to the outcome of the market [5]. This is relevant to our study because it motivates us to use headline sentiment as an explanatory variable for stock returns. Similarly, Engelberg and Parsons demonstrate that media coverage is as important as the content itself [2]. More covered sectors, such as the technology and financial sectors, are expected to be more tradable using news headlines. This drove us to make a balanced mode that adds another dimension to our research by equalizing the headline counts for each sector. This separates the predictive capability of headlines from media coverage. Additionally, in Engelberg and Parsons's research, they found that the timing of news is important to judge its effect on trading [2]. For example, media released after market hours would not affect same-day trading. Hence, we built our model so that it predicts returns on the next day the news is released, and applies a leakage guard to prevent look-ahead bias.

To analyze the polarity of the news headlines, we used the VADER sentiment analysis tool. VADER is attuned to short headline texts in the media without the need for extensive context information [4]. This is ideal for the logistic regression model because news headlines are typically short titles created to be concise by design. Additionally, VADER

was built to measure a short text’s intensity on a continuous scale [4]. We use this to translate intensity into a feature that is used to predict the probability that the stock will rise the next day.

Research done by Eugene Fama provides extensive evidence as to how industries differ in terms of return and risk behavior [3]. This can be applied to the 11 GICS sectors, and our study expands on this by examining whether sectors can differ based on news headline sentiment. So, while prior studies establish a connection between the stock market and the media, this paper evaluates the connection at the sector-level and tests whether sentiment can predict future short-term returns.

Recent financial models, such as FinBERT, offer context-aware sentiment analysis and represent a natural extension of our work [1]. However, we chose to use VADER due to its simplicity and suitability for short headlines.

3 Data Collection and Processing

This study combines three datasets to create the training data for the logistic regression model. First, we scrape Wikipedia’s S&P 500 companies to collect tickers and the sector they belong to. Specifically, we scrape tickers (`src/12_build_universe_sp500.py`) and GICS sectors and load them into `data/clean/universe.csv`. After running this, the universe is populated with 113 tickers and their corresponding sectors, saved as a CSV file. We have also imported the Yahoo Finance dataset to fetch the prices of the stocks listed in the universe (`src/10_fetch_prices.py`). We store 303,567 rows of OHLCV data in `data/raw/prices/prices.parquet` to train the logistic regression model. To get the headlines, `src/21_fetch_headlines_gdelt.py` fetches them monthly from the GDELT Doc API headlines. This creates `data/raw/headlines/headlines.parquet`, which contains 24,668 raw headlines before filtering them. A specific feature that is implemented to prevent look-ahead bias is the leakage guard. It filters the headlines to be before 3:30 PM ET. Anything after this time has information that the strategy could not observe before the market closed. Without the leakage guard, the performance of the model would be artificially raised. After the leakage guard is applied to the current dataset, 11,118 GDELT news headlines remain. Following this, the pipeline maps news headlines to tickers using aliases. To do this, the headlines needed to be normalized by removing whitespace and converting to lowercase letters. Utilizing VADER sentiment analysis in `src/40_make_features.py`, we evaluate the sentiment of the headlines on a scale of -1.0 to 1.0. Next, we compute statistics for headlines: `headline_cnt` (number of headlines), `sent_mean` (average VADER score), and `sent_max` (max VADER score). There is also data for each ticker’s forward one-day return in the stock market in the training data, used to backtest the logistic regression model on real price

fluctuations. The headline features are saved to `data/clean/features_headlines.parquet` and then merged with the aforementioned forward one-day return (`fwd_ret`) to finally form the labeled training data (`data/clean/training_data.csv`).

4 Methodology

As described previously, we have three inputs for the logistic regression classifier: `headline_cnt`, `sent_mean`, and `sent_max`. Sectors are one-hot encoded to transform categorical data into binary data. For example, if a ticker is in the healthcare sector, the feature `sector_Healthcare` is encoded as 1, and if not, it is encoded as 0. The target is `label = 1(fwd_ret > 0)`, and the model is attempting to predict whether the next day's return is positive or not. Missing `fwd_ret` datapoints in the last day of the series are dropped to clean the data. We also use an 80/20 split of our data by date for training/testing. Using a split based on time simulates real trading activity. Additionally, 80% of the data is used for training to have a meaningful training dataset while still leaving enough to test the logistic regression. Accordingly, the model trains 2757 rows and tests on 646 rows in `data/clean/training_data.csv`. The data is split by date on 2023-03-01, to have an 80/20 split. Next, we selected a binary classifier based on a logistic regression model that predicts the probability of the next day's return being positive. This model was chosen due to its simplicity and the ability to rank output probabilities (`p_up`) clearly. We scaled the features using `StandardScaler` from the Python library `scikit-learn`, fit on the training data, and then applied it to the test data. The regression model (`sklearn.linear_model.LogisticRegression`, `max_iter=1000`, `random_state=42`) is then fit onto the scaled data. During the testing period, the model determines the `p_up` for each ticker and sorts them to retrieve the top 5 tickers with the highest probability to go up on the following day. Then, the top 5 tickers are traded on the next day, and we average the actual returns of each ticker. These averages are recorded in `data/clean/equity_curve.csv` and used to calculate the portfolio's returns and Sharpe ratios. The daily portfolio returns are determined by the transaction cost (10 bps) subtracted from the average `fwd_ret`. Additionally, we create `data/clean/sector_daily_returns.csv` from the selected ticker's daily returns by sector. Once the model finishes executing, we compute performance metrics of annualized arithmetic and geometric returns, annualized volatility, Sharpe ratio, max drawdown (worst case loss in equity curve), and number of trading days and non-zero trading days (`src/50_train_backtest`). To test the model's validity, we ran a one-sample t-test on each sector on both weekly and daily returns. Since we test multiple sectors, we apply a Benjamini-Hochberg FDR correction to the p-values. The outputs are stored in the files `data/clean/sector_ttest.csv` and `data/clean/sector_ttest_weekly.csv`. The sectors often have a high p-value due to the low number of non-zero trade days.

5 Results

The portfolio results come from a test window that was not in the training data. There were 659 test days, 36 non-zero trading days, a 5.5% annual return (arithmetic), a 6.56% annual volatility, and a portfolio Sharpe ratio of 0.842. The cumulative return rate is shown in Figure 1, displaying modest returns overall with a 5.5% annual return rate. The top 3 sectors that performed the best in our logistic regression model were the technology, industrials, and financials sectors. They had relatively high Sharpe ratios, with the technology sector having the highest of 1.11. A Sharpe ratio of 1.11 suggests that the technology has adequate risk-adjusted returns solely based on news headlines. The technology sector also had a relatively high number of non-zero trading days (21). Weaker sectors like the healthcare and real estate sectors had sparse signals and low annual return rates. Communication services had the highest number of non-zero days with a low annual return rate. This shows that higher trade volume does not guarantee a higher Sharpe ratio. Table 2 covers these statistics at the sector level, and Figure 2 visualizes the Sharpe ratios across sectors. The balanced mode, which equalizes trades across sectors, is used as a robustness check. It reduced the Sharpe ratios for low-coverage sectors, indicating that coverage and tradability are closely related. The t-test results in `sector_ttest.csv` show that most sectors have high p-values after correction, as expected due to the limited number of active trades. These results support Hypothesis 2, because news headlines' predictive power did vary substantially across sectors, with high coverage sectors performing well. Hypothesis 1 is partially supported, as a subset of the sectors performs effectively, fueled by headline sentiment.

6 Figures and Tables

Figure 1: Cumulative return

Figure 2: Sharpe ratios by sector

Figure 3: Sharpe ratios by sector under the balanced trading mode.

Metric	Value
Universe tickers	113
Universe sectors	12
Prices rows	304015
Prices date range	2015-01-02 to 2025-10-31
Headlines raw	24668
Headlines after leakage guard	15123
Matched ticker-days	4503
Matched date range	2017-01-03 to 2025-10-03
Unique tickers with features	111

Table 1: Portfolio-level performance metrics for the out-of-sample test period.

Sector	Ann Return	Ann Vol	Sharpe	Max DD	Days	Non-zero Days
Technology	7.08%	6.39%	1.11	-4.63%	659	21
Industrials	1.30%	1.86%	0.70	-1.88%	659	15
Financials	1.34%	2.01%	0.67	-2.33%	659	13
Materials	1.05%	3.20%	0.33	-2.66%	659	11
Consumer Staples	0.58%	1.88%	0.31	-1.86%	659	13
Communication Services	1.38%	5.64%	0.24	-9.92%	659	32
Utilities	0.38%	2.73%	0.14	-4.57%	659	15
Energy	-0.82%	4.73%	-0.17	-7.67%	659	16
Consumer Discretionary	-1.24%	3.82%	-0.32	-7.31%	659	13
Real Estate	-1.84%	3.75%	-0.49	-4.98%	659	18
Healthcare	-1.35%	2.71%	-0.50	-5.03%	659	13

Table 2: Portfolio-level performance metrics for the out-of-sample test period.

7 Discussion

Overall, our results have shown that news predictability varies across sectors, with sectors like technology and financials having the best Sharpe ratios. Reconsidering hypothesis 1 (news-headline sentiment can effectively predict next-day returns in the stock market), the regression model partially supports it. In view of the entire portfolio, we have a modest Sharpe ratio of 0.842 and an annual return rate of 5.5%. This shows that using news-headline sentiment exclusively can predict the market, although to a low extent. Hypothesis 2, news-driven tradability differs by sector, wherein some sectors express stronger risk-adjusted performance than others, is supported by our research. We found significant variation between the Sharpe ratios of the 11 GICS sectors, ranging from -0.5 to 1.11. This demonstrates the intrinsic differences in sectors affected by news headlines. Sector differences can be due to news intensity, news coverage, event-driven behavior, etc. We have also found that high news coverage (non-zero days) doesn't guarantee better returns because market noise can still dominate, as seen in the communication services sector. The balanced mode returns moderately similar rankings, with the only notable changes in the industrials and consumer discretionary sectors; however dampens the Sharpe values of each sector. In the technology sector, the Sharpe ratio changes from 1.11 to 0.86. This indicates that media coverage can amplify performance, because when coverage is constant, most of the Sharpe values are lower. Media coverage and tonality both play a role in the media's predictive power. These findings are consistent with what Tetlock found, as the

balanced mode has shown that the tone matters, and variations are not only due to media coverage. Our results further expand on Fama & French’s study of differences in industries by connecting different factors, such as media coverage and tonality.

8 Limitations

The main limitation of the statistical testing is that it has low statistical power and a short testing window. The average p-value of all the sectors was 0.432, and they ranged from 0.06 to 0.82 (data

clean

sector_ttest_weekly.csv). This is due to the low number of non-zero trading days and a short testing window of 2 years. However, our goal was to study patterns at the sector-level, not to prove a hypothesis definitively. Finding the Sharpe ratios and non-zero days still remains informative and warrants future research to be done. Another minor limitation is that the headline sentiment ignores the full article and its contents. This could lead to lower accuracy; however, it did follow our original research question and kept the logistic regression simpler. We also had fixed trading rules, such as an assumed 10 bps transaction cost and only the top 5 tickers per day. This was intentional to keep calculations simple and have easy sector comparisons. Lastly, we had a benchmark performance using a SPY buy-and-hold strategy, and it exhibited a higher Sharpe ratio of 1.48. This reflects a bullish time period for the market and highlights that this was an exploratory study about signal detection in sector-level markets, not a market-beating trading strategy.

9 Conclusion

Our research has shown the predictive potential of news headlines on the stock market. Our Hypothesis 1 about the media’s predictive power was partially supported, and Hypothesis 2 was supported due to the clear sector dispersion. The portfolio’s Sharpe ratio tested on an out-of-sample window was 0.842, and Technology had the highest Sharpe ratio of 1.11. The core insight gained from this study was that the sentiment signal is greatly affected by noise, but can still predict certain sectors. Additionally, media coverage alone does not guarantee predictability. Future research can be done by extending the testing window to get statistically significant results and testing other models, such as a decision tree using headline sentiment.

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